

PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPIRITUAL IMMUNITY IN YOUTH

Radjapov Rustam Ramazanovich and Pirnazarov Roman Aralovich
Teachers of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Аннотация

Ушбу мақолада ёшлар орасида маънавий иммунитет тушунчаси ва уни шакллантиришда психологик механизмлар таҳлил қилинади. Маънавий иммунитет — бу ёш шахсининг ташқи салбий таъсирларга, ёт ғоялар ва бузғунчи таъсирларга нисбатан бардошли бўлиши, ички қарашлари ва қадриятларига таянган ҳолда ўзини сақлай олиш қобилиятидир. Мақолада ушбу иммунитетни ривожлантиришда эмпатия, рефлексия, ички назорат, мотивация ва ижтимоий тафаккур каби психологик омилларнинг аҳамияти ёритилади.

Калит сўзлар: маънавий иммунитет, психологик ёндашув, ёшлар ривож, ички назорат, эмпатия, шахс тарбияси, психологик барқарорлик.

Аннотация

В статье анализируется понятие духовного иммунитета у молодежи и психологические механизмы его формирования. Духовный иммунитет — это способность молодого человека противостоять внешним негативным воздействиям, чуждым идеям, деструктивным влияниям и сохранять себя на основе своих внутренних взглядов и ценностей. В статье подчеркивается важность психологических факторов, таких как эмпатия, рефлексия, внутренний контроль, мотивация и социальное мышление, в развитии этого иммунитета.

Ключевые слова: духовный иммунитет, психологический подход, развитие молодежи, внутренний контроль, эмпатия, воспитание личности, психологическая устойчивость.

Abstract

This article analyzes the concept of spiritual immunity among young people and the psychological mechanisms involved in its formation. Spiritual immunity is the ability of a young person to withstand external negative influences, alien ideas and destructive influences, to protect himself, relying on his inner views and values. The article highlights the importance of such psychological factors as empathy, reflection, internal control, motivation and social thinking in the development of this immunity.

Keywords: spiritual immunity, psychological approach, youth development, internal control, empathy, personal upbringing, psychological stability.

Today, in the conditions of information overload, the influence of global culture and the widespread spread of foreign ideas, the spiritual stability of the younger generation is becoming one of the most important problems. From this point of view, the formation and development of spiritual immunity in young people is an urgent task today. Spiritual immunity is based on a person's internal spiritual strength, moral position and ability to perceive the truth. This immunity is an important factor in educating young people as socially active and responsible individuals, making them resistant to various threats, negative influences and moral crises[1].

Spiritual immunity is the ability of a person to resist various external negative influences, relying on his spiritual stability, personal moral values and spiritual views. It is a strong internal support formed in the heart and mind of a person, ensuring that a young person does not lose his way

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

in various difficult situations that arise in life, and stands firm against foreign ideas, spiritual threats and destructive influences.

Spiritual immunity develops through a person's belief in universal and national values, correctly formed life goals, personal philosophy, and the ability to understand and act on such high virtues as honesty, justice, conscience, and humanism. It not only helps to resist negative moral influences, but also encourages young people to develop positive qualities such as self-awareness, independent formation of their own views and positions, and active participation in social life[2].

Young people with spiritual immunity occupy a strong position in life. They are able to think independently, critically analyze, and make the right decisions without losing their personal views even during various information attacks, foreign ideas, and moral crises. At the same time, such young people have the ability to protect themselves from mass pressure, negative influences on the Internet, and destructive moral trends in the virtual environment, and are formed as active individuals living in spiritual balance.

Therefore, the development of spiritual immunity is one of the priority tasks of upbringing and education, which is of decisive importance in the upbringing of the younger generation as a mature person. The formation of this immunity requires a deep psychological and educational approach, taking into account the inner world of a person, spiritual needs, moral views and life experience.

Psychological approaches play an important role in the process of forming spiritual immunity. These approaches are based on working with the inner world, feelings and way of thinking of a person and serve as an effective tool in educating young people as spiritually mature individuals. Through psychological approaches, a person forms not only knowledge and moral concepts, but also the ability to apply them in life.

Firstly, reflection is a person's ability to consciously reflect on his own actions and internal states, to understand himself. The formation of reflection in young people allows them to draw the right conclusions from their mistakes and successes, and to realize internal development.

Secondly, the sense of internal control is the ability of a person to control their own emotions, actions and impulses. This characteristic encourages young people to exercise self-control, make decisions with restraint and act responsibly. Young people with high internal control are less susceptible to external influences and remain true to their principles.

Third, empathy is the ability to deeply feel, understand, and empathize with the feelings of others. Empathetic youth are able to establish strong social connections with people around them, and live an active, humane life in society.

Fourth, social thinking is associated with a person's awareness of himself as a member of society, understanding his social role, and feeling responsible. This ability develops a person's recognition of collective interests, civic duty, and patriotism.

Fifth, motivation is a person's desire for spiritual goals, self-development, and the need for constant improvement. Motivation, as a source of internal strength, encourages a person to act, ensures consistent action, and continuous development.

These psychological elements, being interconnected, have a profound effect on the spiritual immune system of a young person. They play an important role in shaping the worldview, moral position, thinking culture, and decision-making ability of young people. Therefore, it is necessary to use psychological approaches in a targeted and systematic manner to strengthen spiritual immunity.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

In modern society, there are various threats that affect the spiritual stability and inner world of young people. These factors, if not adequately analyzed and prevented, can lead to a weakening of spiritual immunity in young people and a departure from personal values.

First, the destructive content spread through information technologies and the Internet poses a great danger. Through the one-sided influence of propaganda, violence, and mass culture, young people can distance themselves from their national and human values and lose their ability to think critically. Content on the Internet that is not logically based and full of false information has a negative impact on young people whose ability to make informed choices is not yet fully formed.

Secondly, cultural alienation, that is, the process of moving away from national traditions and universal human values, is a phenomenon that is accelerating, especially under the influence of globalization. Ignoring national culture leads to a loss of identity and a tendency to alien ideas. This causes a young person to have an identity crisis, that is, a state of inability to understand who they are.

Thirdly, social injustices, that is, unemployment, inequality, and imbalance in the distribution of opportunities, can form a pessimistic attitude towards life in young people. Growing up in an unjust environment, there is a risk of a decrease in spiritual stability and social trust, and apathy towards society.

Fourthly, the insufficient formation of personal consciousness, that is, the lack of clarity of personal goals and life direction, also leaves a young person open to influence. A young person whose consciousness and spirit are not in order may not be able to find himself in his life and often fall under the influence of others. In this case, young people cannot independently form their own values, which leads to a weakening of spiritual immunity.

Fifth, the lack of support from the family and educational institutions creates a huge spiritual void for the young person. The lack of parental attention, the failure of teachers and mentors to fully fulfill the educational function, deprives the young person of social and spiritual support. A young person growing up in such an environment may feel lonely, depressed and worthless[3].

False images spread through the press, cinema, music and advertising lead to a distorted perception of reality in young people, idealization of foreign ideas and lifestyles. Such mass influences, if not critically analyzed, lead to spiritual depression and instability.

The factors that threaten the spirituality of young people are multifaceted and interrelated. To prevent them and reduce their harm, it is necessary to systematically take psychological, educational and social measures. In this way, it will be possible to strengthen the spiritual immunity of young people.

Strategies used to form and strengthen spiritual immunity in young people should be systematic, purposeful, and based on active participation. In this regard, interactive psychodidactic approaches, exercises aimed at developing personal thinking, and the qualitative organization of the educational environment play an important role.

Firstly, interactive psychodidactic methods, that is, exercises that involve students and young people in active participation, give effective results in the formation of spiritual immunity. These methods include exercises such as analysis of problem situations, debates, and "school of life". A young person who participates in problematic situations acquires the skills to critically analyze reality, substantiate his point of view with evidence, and find solutions from a spiritual point of view. These methods serve to accumulate social experience in young people and form a confident position in making life decisions.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

Secondly, through activities that stimulate personal reflection, a young person has the opportunity to deeply analyze his feelings and thoughts. Such activities include exercises such as writing diaries, writing essays, compiling analytical reflections, and re-evaluating life events in his own mind. Thanks to these exercises, a young person has the opportunity to form his spiritual values, life goals, and personal philosophy.

Thirdly, developing empathy in young people is also an important component of spiritual immunity. Exercises that teach understanding, feeling others, and maintaining humanity in relationships — including role-playing, role-playing, and discussing various social scenarios — help young people develop emotional intelligence, compassion, and social responsibility. This helps them avoid indifference, violence, or excessively individualistic views.

Fourthly, the role of educational activities in developing spiritual immunity is invaluable. Meetings, lectures, creative dialogues, reading evenings, and spiritual and educational events that promote spiritual values help young people to firmly establish concepts such as goodness, truth, conscience, and a high goal. Such activities enrich the spiritual environment and have a positive spiritual impact.

Fifth, education in partnership between family and school is the main foundation for the formation of spiritual immunity. If the psychological needs of a child and young person are correctly understood and supported in a timely manner, their internal stability, self-confidence and social responsibility increase. As a result of targeted work carried out in cooperation with parents, teachers and psychologists, the educational process becomes holistic and systematic. This forms a conscious attitude to life, the ability to make the right choice and the ability to distinguish between spiritual alternatives in a young person.

These strategies aimed at developing spiritual immunity serve as the foundation for the harmonious development of young people, incorporating individual, psychological and moral approaches to the person in the educational process.

Spiritual immunity is an important psychological and social phenomenon that reflects the formation of a young person's internal stability, worldview and spiritual position. It determines a person's strong outlook on life, forms the ability to resist threats and negative influences, and protects a person from spiritual decline. The development of this immunity is directly related, first of all, to personal psychological mechanisms - reflection, empathy, internal control, social thinking and spiritual motivation.

Through the targeted use of psychological approaches based on these mechanisms in the educational process, it is possible to form spiritual immunity in the younger generation. In this process, the cooperation of teachers, psychologists and parents, the combined activities of the family and school as an educational system, are of particular importance. Therefore, in strengthening the spirituality of young people, it is necessary to effectively use interactive psychodidactic methods, exercises that develop personal thinking, social activities and trainings that develop empathy.

Based on the above-mentioned scientific conclusions, it can be said that young people with spiritual immunity mature as well-rounded individuals who have found their place in society, have internal discipline and a high sense of responsibility, and have formed a culture of thinking. They become citizens who actively participate not only in their personal lives, but also in the spiritual and moral stability of society.

References:

1. Khamidov A. Psychology of spiritual and moral development. Tashkent: Scientific and pedagogical publishing house, 2020.
2. Ganieva M. Methods of developing thinking and moral education. Tashkent: Pedagogical publishing house, 2021.
3. Toshpulatov Sh. Psychology of youth and the social environment. Tashkent: "Science and Development" publishing house, 2022. 75 pages
4. Erkinovich A. O. ДАВЛАТ БОШҚАРУВ ТИЗИМИДА ИНТЕРНЕТ-КОММУНИКАЦИЯНИНГ ЎРНИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND LEARNING. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 475-482.
5. Алляров О. Э. ИНТЕРНЕТНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙИЙ-СИЁСИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАР ТИЗИМИДА САМАРАЛИ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ОМИЛЛАРИ //JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 6. – С. 27-34.
6. Erkinovich A. O., Kuchkar A. The Role of Information Technologies in the Field of Science and Technology Development //The Peerian Journal. – 2022. – Т. 12. – С. 120-128.
7. ALLAYAROV O. GLOBALLASHUV JARAYONIDA INTERNET TEXNOLOGIYALARINING YOSHLAR MA'NAVIY-AHLOQIY TA'LIM TARBIYASIDAGI O'RNI //АСТА NUUZ. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 1.10. 1. – С. 38-40.
8. Narimbayevich A. R. VATANPARVARLIK-MILLIY G'UYAMIZ ASOSI //Научный Фокус. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 19. – С. 602-606.
9. Narmanov A., Rajabov E. The geometry of vector fields and two dimensional heat equation //International electronic journal of geometry. – 2023. – Т. 16. – №. 1. – С. 73-80.
10. Narmanov A., Rajabov E. The Geometry of Vector Fields and two Dimensional Heat Equation //Journal of Applied Nonlinear Dynamics. – 2024. – Т. 13. – №. 03. – С. 431-438.
11. Ruziboyevich R. R. THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER IN EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2024. – Т. 54. – С. 961-964.
12. Sharipbayevich S. A., Qurbonnazrovich A. Y., To'Xtajon X. SORAXON XALFA-XORAZM MADANIY HAYOTINING YETUK NAMOYONDASI //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 58-61.
13. Sharipbayevich S. A., Choriyevich S. B. ROVIYA ATADJANOVA XORAZM RAQSI MALIKASI //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 13-16.
14. Burgutovich S. B. OLIY HARBIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI //IMRAS. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 6. – С. 290-293.
15. Burgutovich S. B. CREATIVE PEDAGOGY IN HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATION BASICS OF USE //Western European Journal of Linguistics and Education. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 1-4.